

**FORMATION OF AN ONLINE FORMAT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF LANGUAGE LITERACY
IN THE EDUCATION OF CITIZENS OF KAZAKHSTAN****Kudabaeva K.,***candidate of Pedagogical Sciences,
Abai Kazakh Pedagogical University,
Almaty, Kazakhstan**H-index: 2**<https://orcid.org/0000-0002--0034-858X>,***Yerserikuly D.***Magister 7M02120-Graphic design**<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10451775>***Abstract**

This article analyzes the processes of development and promotion of websites aimed at providing services related to online language courses in the territory of the Republic of Kazakhstan. The authors of the article also focused in their work on web design, the role of the Internet in the pedagogical aspect of language courses, and the analysis of Kazakhstan's use of language education in an online format. This article examines how the World-wide Network, websites and online education have contributed to the learning of the Kazakh language. Statistics on Internet penetration among citizens of Kazakhstan. Discussions on the importance of language proficiency as a way of obtaining information for Kazakhstanis and communication in the foreign sphere. In addition, the current institutional members of Shea are also members of CIQG. At the same time, it is noted that Kazakhstan has been implemented in three directions. What preferences do the citizens of Kazakhstan have in choosing a language and what Internet resources do they use to develop their language literacy. The future use of artificial intelligence is also given. How the process of creating Online courses takes place, and the advantages and recommendations of this type of training are presented in statistics and dynamics.

Keywords: Online, course, web analytics, web design, education, research, information, technology.

Introduction

An urgent problem today is the enormous progress in the transfer of information around the world, which in the 21st century has provided the world community with new opportunities in all spheres of human activity, in the field of education, and the transfer of information has become more flexible and accessible. However, the membership list of CIGA CHAO International Quality Group (KING) contributes to the understanding of international quality guarantees and the promotion of high-quality higher education in today's competitive and international world. Thus, the current institutional members of Chea are also members of CIQG. Kazakhstan is a member in three areas: firstly, the Eurasian Center for Accreditation and Quality Assurance in Higher Education and Healthcare; secondly, the independent Agency for Accreditation and Rating; thirdly, it was introduced by the independent Agency for Quality Assurance in Education [1], which is a great achievement. In addition, the choice of the topic of using the online format in education for the development of language literacy is not accidental, since the Order of the Minister of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated March 20, 2015 No. 137. Order No. 122 approved the requirements for educational organizations to provide distance learning and the principles of organizing the educational process for distance learning and programs of higher and (or) postgraduate education in the form of online learning. Order of the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated April 22, 2015 No. 10768. In Chapter 1. Requirements for educational organizations in the implementation of distance learning, in paragraph 2) the functioning of an

educational management information system, including a website, an educational portal, an automated system for providing credit training technology and an education management platform, including a set of digital educational resources; [2]. The difference between educational management information systems is that the management platform includes an educational website, but does not involve web design. This leads to the hypothesis that in the modern situation it is necessary to work on preserving the cultural heritage of each nation, reflecting national value, whereas in the era of computer technology in the process of globalization, taking into account the importance of preserving the uniqueness of the peoples of the world, however, in the educational portal of national identity, the development of language literacy in the Republic of Kazakhstan web design It must be scientifically justified so that we can preserve the cultural heritage of our people - We protect our cultural values from the process of globalization in the age of computer technology. However, given the importance of preserving the identity of one's national language code in the global modern world in the Republic of Kazakhstan, therefore, we decided on the title of the article: "Using the online format for the development of language literacy in the education of citizens of Kazakhstan."

Research goals:

- Studying foreign materials and materials from CIS countries, as well as the World Wide Web, websites and online education, promoting knowledge of any language web design (collection of materials).

- Analysis of the processes of development and promotion of websites aimed at providing services related to online language courses in the social sphere of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

- Determination of the importance of web design, Internet videos in any direction (by which university) in the aspect of language courses, analysis of the use of language education by Kazakhstanis in an online format.

- Identifying and conducting practical and experimental work on web design in order to develop one's own language literacy, aimed at developing and formalizing objects of the Internet information environment, for the purpose of ensuring high consumer qualities and aesthetic qualities.

Materials, methods and organization of the research form.

Tools and technologies

Web designers use different tools depending on what part of the production process they are involved in. These tools are updated over time with new standards and software, but their principles remain the same. Web designers use vector and raster graphics editors to create web images or develop prototypes. Technologies used to create websites include W3C standards such as HTML and CSS, which can be coded by hand or created using WYSIWYG editing software. Other tools that web designers can use include markup validators. [3] and include other usability and accessibility testing tools to ensure that their websites comply with Internet accessibility guidelines [4]. W3C Markup Validation Service. validator.w3.org. application date: April 5, 2022 Archived from the original on February 22, 2011. W3C Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI). Home (English). Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI). Retrieved April 5, 2022. Archived from the original on April 5, 2022. 1) Selecting an Idea and Topic: Choose a topic and idea that you have experience with. Perhaps this is something you are interested in. 2) Target Audience: Determine your target audience. This helps tailor the content and style of teaching. 3) Market research. Do your research to determine if there is a demand for your course. Review existing courses in your area to determine their popularity and appeal. 4) planning and structuring: create an overall course outline. Determine how the material will be structured, how many lessons, what content formats will be used (video, text, assignments, etc.). 5) Select a platform. Choose a platform to host your courses. For example, it could be a popular educational platform like Udemy, Coursera, or you can create your own website. 6) Content Creation: Create content for your lessons. This may include recording video lessons, writing texts, preparing assignments and tests. Forms of research organization; testing: test the course on a small group of people to get feedback. This helps improve the quality and effectiveness of the course; Marketing: Develop a marketing strategy to attract students. This may include the use of social media, website creation, advertising and other methods; student support: provide a mechanism to support students. This includes forums, Q&A emails, webinars, and more. may enter; Update and Improve: Once launched, con-

tinually update and improve the course based on feedback and changes in the industry. As an analysis of the work shows, many platforms have been created based on this principle, offering online learning, including language courses. Online language learning has its benefits. Some of them: flexible schedule: students can study in their free time; access to resources: extensive educational materials are available online; personalization of training: choice of materials and difficulty level; save time and money: no need to travel and stay; Replayability: Students can return to materials for revision. Global community: the opportunity to communicate with native speakers from different countries; use of technology: interactive applications and platforms enrich learning; Online testing: quick test of knowledge and results; effectively measure progress: many platforms offer success statistics. The result is accessibility for all: education can be achieved by people of all financial levels. The learning management information system we proposed in the discussion is a learning management platform that includes a website rather than a web design. Therefore, the hypothesis itself, in the current situation - in the age of computer technology, in the process of globalization, if it is necessary to work on preserving the cultural heritage of each nation, reflecting national value, taking into account the importance of preserving the identity of the peoples of the world, in the educational portal of national identity, in the development of linguistic literacy in RK, its own network - It is necessary to scientifically substantiate the project, and then we will preserve the cultural heritage of our people, reflecting national value in the modern situation - taking into account the importance of preserving the originality of the national code of the Republic of Kazakhstan in the era of computer technology, globalization processes, in the global modern world. We also understand that web design is a type of Graphic Design aimed at designing and designing objects of the Internet information environment, designed to provide high consumer qualities and aesthetic qualities. D. V. Borodaev also justifies web design with web programming, emphasizes the specifics of the disciplinary activity of a web designer, and classifies web design as a type of graphic design [3].

Process and result

Based on the concept of cultural national value, the creation of a unique design involves a completely unique development for a specific order. Depending on the professionalism and economic and social policies of the national company, the web designer develops the idea and design concept completely independently. He also receives a set of requirements (color, style, etc.), expectations and ideas from the client or creative director (art director) and tries to follow this direction when developing the layout. Most clients mistakenly identify the web designer and webmaster and entrust him with the publication of the site. Sometimes a designer can offer a design solution based on templates, in which case the work will be faster and cheaper for the customer. Consequently, some designers even specialize in creating design mockups to sell as ready-made templates, which can then be purchased and used by less experienced designers or webmasters to create their

own websites (mostly without custom design). Web design development involves customizing and customizing the template. The web designer's image is displayed on the website page, the final product of his work is the design layout. This image is multi-layered, where at the discretion of the designer, each part is a separate layer that is superimposed on other layers - images, so that refinements, replacements, reconstructions and other tasks can be easily performed. It contains photographs, intricate collages, illustrations, text overlays, and unique icons related to the idea and purpose. Separate layouts are sometimes created for the home page and subpage, with additions or changes to suit the theme of the page. However, in some cases, the image may be a vector or raster image originally created in Adobe Illustrator, Adobe Photoshop, GIMP, or another visual editor (such as Scribus or Inkscape), but the image is usually converted to a raster format for layout. Consequently, in subsequent years, a changed paradigm emerged in which the final product of a web designer is a design layout with vector graphics controlled by the designer, not as an image, but as an interactive field, as in a graphics editor. In addition, all manipulations with interactive field elements are described as cascading tables with CSS styles applied by the layouts. For example, Figma, Sketch are suitable). For example, Single Link of the above application is also suitable for showing the client, where it is quite possible to present the design in the form of an interactive prototype rather than a static display. Thus, the website is its face, a virtual official office that has its place in the graphic space of the World Wide Web (Internet). Then the importance of websites can hardly be overestimated; the platform can play a different role for an organization, replacing several employees. Internet platform operator, sales manager, consultant, guide, graphic designer, marketer, teacher, etc. However, such a huge information leap throughout the world has given the global community new opportunities in all spheres of human activity in the 21st century, and learning and the transfer of information have become much more flexible and accessible. We devote this article to the pedagogical aspect of the online space. How much has this digitalization affected the general education of citizens of Kazakhstan? To do this, it was necessary to start with analysis and statistics of how many people use the World Wide Web in Kazakhstan. The data from the well-known Wikipedia website is as follows: The Statistics Agency of the Republic of Kazakhstan, as well as other monitoring companies, regularly conduct research on the Internet audience of Kazakhstan. The number of individual Internet users in Kazakhstan has shown strong growth in the early years of the 21st century. According to JSC Kazcontent, in 2007 the Internet audience accounted for 12.3% of the population of the Republic of Kazakhstan and 26.4% of the urban population; at the end of 2010, these figures were 25.7% and 44.1%, respectively[6]. Internet user statistics by year:

- 2000 - 70,000 Internet users (0.5%)
- 2005 - 400,000 Internet users (2.7%)
- 2007 - 1,247,000 Internet users (8.5%)

According to TNS Central Asia, the Kaznet audience at the beginning of 2016 reached 63.3% of the total population of the republic. At the same time, the level of Internet penetration in the group of 15-24 years old reached 97%. And in the age group 25-44 - 92%.

In 2016, it was recorded for the first time that the share of Internet users in Kazakhstan accessing the Internet from mobile devices began to dominate.

By 2022, 17.3 million of the 19.5 million population in Kazakhstan use the Internet, with penetration of 89.2%. Thus, statistics show us and allow us to conclude that all groups of the country's population have access to the Internet. Also, such a trend as little involvement with the World Wide Web among the adult population is becoming a thing of the past. Statistics on the distribution of Internet access among citizens of Kazakhstan show that Kazakhstanis receive most of their content from the World Wide Web. This can be seen in photographs 1, 2, 3, 4 as evidence. Figure 1 shows web design. However, the dominant languages in the Kazakh network are Russian, Kazakh and English. All schools in Kazakhstan teach three languages, including English. All educational institutions, colleges, universities, higher education institutions, institutes are trilingual oriented. This gives our students, as well as foreign students, the opportunity to study without being constrained by the language issue. Knowledge of three languages is a great advantage for Kazakhstanis. In terms of prevalence (the total number of people who speak the language), Russian was the eighth language in the world in 2022 (258.2 million), after English (1.5 billion native speakers). Kazakhs, who speak three languages, have the opportunity to communicate with 1.7 billion people around the world and demonstrate their language skills in more than 70 countries. They can also get information, knowledge and content in these languages on the World Wide Web. More than half of the websites and web pages on the Internet use English as their primary language. As of 2019, English will account for 54% of all content on the Internet. However, its share is gradually declining due to the rapid growth of other language segments of the Internet. The Russian language occupies 6% of the world Internet space. These statistics show the importance of learning both your native and foreign languages. Anyone who strives to enrich their knowledge by speaking a new language creates the opportunity for themselves to be understood in every corner of the world. Also, a person has the opportunity to understand this world through the prism of different cultures, make discoveries, conduct scientific research, study, work, and also develop spiritually and mentally. Of course, nowadays the Internet greatly contributes to the process of learning languages. It is noticeable how many courses, applications and sites providing language learning services are appearing in the online space. This abundance of resources is a response to demand from the citizens themselves. Many residents of Kazakhstan strive to master various languages, and this desire continues to grow every year. Which organizations offer their services to people on the Internet? What online platforms do they have? How does the process of learning a language happen in the online space? What are the benefits? We will consider

answers to such questions below. The process of creating online courses goes through many stages: from a conceptual concept to a full-fledged educational product for citizens. Of course, it is worth noting the differences between the online learning format and the traditional one. What are the advantages and disadvantages compared to other types of training? Having studied dozens of popular platforms on the Internet, the general concept of their articles and recommendations for creating online courses includes the general steps to create an online platform that will offer ongoing online courses on a specific vocational education that will meet the requirements of a future client. The sequence of creating online courses requires a lot of financial resources and financial literacy, because creating such an important project requires different skills and abilities. The organization contains many different professional activities and professional employees working at different stages of the creation of this project. Here are some general suggestions and tips from various sources on online platforms:

Conclusions and Recommendations:

- Foreign and CIS materials, as well as the World Wide Web, sites and online education that contribute to the knowledge of what language were studied? web design (collection of materials).

- Analyzed the processes of development and promotion of sites aimed at providing services related to online language courses in the social sphere of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

- The importance of web design, the role of the Internet in the pedagogical direction (which university) in terms of language courses, and an analysis of the use of language education by Kazakhstanis in an online format are determined.

- Web design, aimed at developing and formalizing objects of the Internet information environment, designed to provide them with high consumer qualities and aesthetic qualities, in accordance with the wishes of the citizens of Kazakhstan regarding the choice of language and what Internet resources are used. develop language literacy - Experimental work in the form of graphic design was identified and carried out.

This article is intended as a proposal to promote such an important aspect in the field of education as language learning in the online space. Establish the importance, benefits and accessibility of education such as learning languages on the World Wide Web. Research and analysis of the involvement of citizens of Kazakhstan in language literacy. Further polarization of online learning. It is important to promote and improve online platforms and online learning courses for easy access to knowledge that meets the needs of our citizens. The following suggestions can be made.

- Choosing an idea, concept and theme:
- Choose a topic and idea that you have experience with. Perhaps this is something you are interested in and have experience with.
- Target audience:
- Define your target audience. This helps tailor the content and style of teaching.
- Market research:

- Conduct research to determine if there is a demand for your course. Review existing courses in your area to determine their popularity and appeal.

- Planning and structuring:

- Create an overall course plan. Determine how the material will be structured, how many lessons, what content formats will be used (video, text, assignments, etc.).

- Platform selection:

- Choose a platform to deliver your courses. For example, it could be a popular educational platform like Udemy, Coursera, or you can create your own website.

- Content creation:

- Create content for your lessons. This may include recording video lessons, writing texts, preparing assignments and tests.

- Testing:

- Test the course on a small group of people to get feedback. This will help improve the quality and effectiveness of the course.

- Marketing:

- Develop a marketing strategy to attract students. This may include using social media, creating a website, using advertising and other methods.

- Student support:

- Provide a support mechanism for students. This includes forums, Q&A emails, webinars, etc. b. can come in.

- Updates and improvements:

- Once launched, continually update and improve the course based on feedback and changes in the region.

Based on this principle, many platforms have been created that offer online learning, including language courses. The educational product created according to this plan must offer its customers benefits that traditional teaching methods cannot provide. Online language learning has its benefits. Here are some of them: Flexible schedule: students can study at a time convenient for them.

Access to Resources: Extensive educational materials are available online.

Individualization of training: choice of materials and level of difficulty.

Save time and money: no need to travel and stay.

Replayability: Students can return to the materials for revision.

Global community: the opportunity to communicate with native speakers from different countries.

Use of technology: Interactive applications and platforms enrich learning.

Online testing: quick test of knowledge and results.

Measure progress effectively: Many platforms offer success statistics.

Access for everyone: people of different financial levels can get education.

An impressive number of organizations offer similar online courses in the Kazakhstani network for our citizens. Here are the 10 most popular online platforms offering such courses:

- OOGWAY - language training center(oogway.kz)

- Online English language school. Educational platform – EngGO (enggo.kz)
- NAZAR EDUCATION (nazaredu.kz)
- Qlang. Online English courses. Learn English online with Qlang.
- Online English school (jtstudy.kz)
- Online English courses in Kazakhstan: English language school, online learning (bebestschool.kz)

- Online language courses (oqyqazaq.kz)
 - Online English school. Kazakhstan. (truston.kz)
 - Online Education (interpress.kz)
 - Online English courses in Almaty (lingvomania.kz)
- <https://iqaa.kz/gosudarstvennye-programmy>.
https://bilimdinews.kz/?page_id=184553

Figure No. 1 - Web design for using the online format to develop language literacy in the education of citizens of Kazakhstan.

Meirzhan Auelkhanovich talks about the influence of artificial intelligence (AI) on Kazakh culture as follows. Imagine how the advent of the computer and the Internet has changed the life of mankind. even the smartphone itself is worth it. Now artificial intelligence is also penetrating all of our industries. economics and production, business and marketing have already en-

tered and taken their place. In the figure below, Meirzhan Auelkhanovich clearly showed that artificial intelligentsia (AI) directly and indirectly affects Kazakh culture and literature and cannot be excluded from it. However, the analysis was carried out as follows. Firstly, cultural heritage and history: Secondly, art and creativity: Thirdly, language and education: fourth, social changes: fifth, ethical and legislative measures.

Figure No. 2 - Further use of artificial intelligence in the education of citizens of Kazakhstan.

Figure No. 3 Graphic statistics of Internet users by year.

Figure No. 4 Graphic statistics of Internet users by age.

Figure No. 5 Dynamics of Internet users by year.

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